

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 2

Бош муҳаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети Илмий ишлар ва инновациялар бўйича
проректори, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

*Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги*

Jin Young Choi

*Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти*

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаатовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Худоярова Дилдора Рахимовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети №1-сон Акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255*

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент тиббиёт
академияси Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Акбаров Миршавкат Мирломинович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, В.Ваҳидов номидаги
Республика ихтисослаштирилган жарроҳлик маркази*

Саидов Садамир Аброрович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Бабалжанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент педиатрия
тиббиёт институти, Тери-таносил, болалар
тери-таносил касалликлари ва ОИТС
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327*

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касаликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергандовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат стоматология институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, проректор по научной
работе и инновациям Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD кафедры онкологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi

профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой
хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического
госпиталя Сеульского национального университета,
Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и
эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаатовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Худоярова Дилдора Рахимовна

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой
Акушерства и гинекологии №1 Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующий кафедрой
Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской
хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры
акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины
Ташкентской медицинской академии
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

Акбаров Миршавкат Миролимович

доктор медицинских наук,
Республиканский специализированный центр
хирургии имени академика В.Вахидова

Саидов Саидмир Аброрович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский
фармацевтический институт
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский педиатрический
медицинский институт, кафедра Дерматовенерология, детская
дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской
детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Vice-Rector for scientific work
and Innovation, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shaykatovna
PhD Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Khudoyarova Dildora Rakhimovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology,
Samarkand State Medical University No.1
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine,
Tashkent Medical Academy
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Akbarov Mirshavkat Mirolimovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Republican Specialized Center of Surgery
named after academician V.Vakhidov*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Department of Dermatovenerology,
pediatric dermatovenerology and AIDS
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxamatkulovich

*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

1. **Urinbaeva A. Nilufar, Abduganieva F. Dilsuz**
THE PROBLEM OF FETAL GROWTH RETRACTION SYNDROME IN OBSTETRICS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....10

THERAPY

2. **Jakbarova A. Mohida Juraeva A. Mohigul**
CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA.....22
3. **Boltaev J. Kamol, Rizaeva J. Malika**
THE ROLE OF PREDICTORS IN THE FORMATION OF THROMBOSIS IN ATRIAL FIBRILLATION (REVIEW ARTICLE).....27
4. **Akhmedov A. Ibrat, Uralov Sh Rustam, Akhmedova A. Gulchekhra**
THE ROLE OF ANTIFILAGGRIN ANTIBODIES IN THE DIAGNOSIS AND PROGNOSIS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS AT AN EARLY STAGE.....33
5. **Akhmedova Sh. Nilufar, Rizayeva J. Malika**
CHANGES IN ANTITHROMBIN INDICATORS IN ATRIAL FIBRILLATION.....39
6. **Agababyan R. Irina, Djabbarova M. Nafisa**
CURRENT ISSUES IN MODERN TREATMENT OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE.....44
7. **Abdushukurova R. Komila, Akhmedov A. Ibrat**
FOUNDATIONS OF IMMUNOPATHOGENESIS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS: REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....55
8. **Makhatmuradova N.Nargiza**
FEATURES OF HIGH-RESOLUTION COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY IN NONSPECIFIC INTERSTITIAL PNEUMONIA.....66
9. **Akhmedov A. Ibrat, Uralov Sh Rustam, Eshmuratov E. Sardor**
FEATURES OF THE SUBPOPULATION COMPOSITION OF PERIPHERAL BLOOD LYMPHOCYTES IN THE FIRST PERIODS OF THE DISEASE IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS.....73
10. **Kityan S.Aleksandr**
COMPREHENSIVE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE CURRENT EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SITUATION REGARDING THE INCIDENCE AND PREVALENCE OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE(LITERARY REVIEW).....78

SURGERY

11. **Mamanov Ch Muxammad., Arziev A Ismoil, Arzieva B Gulnora**
DIFFERENTIATED SURGICAL TACTICS FOR COMPLICATED FORMS OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS.....83
12. **Zohidova H Sanoat, Mamataliyev R. Abdumalik**
DESPITE THE COMPLEXITY AND SERIOUSNESS OF THE DISEASE, MODERN TREATMENT METHODS CAN ACHIEVE POSITIVE RESULTS AND IMPROVE THE PROGNOSIS OF PATIENTS WITH DESTRUCTIVE PANCREATITIS.....91
13. **Achilov T. Mirzakarim, Ahmedov K. Gayrat, Mirmuxammedov Dj.Nasimjon, Shakulov M. Azizbek**
INTRAGENATION OF PROLOSED RECTUM (CASE FROM PRACTICE).....97

14. **Babajanov S. Akhmadjon, Akhmedov I. Adkham, Shamsiev J. Shokhzod**
IMPROVEMENT OF THE INTRAOPERATIVE THYROMETRY METHOD IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF BENIGN THYROID GLAND PATHOLOGIES.....104
15. **Khursanov E. Yokub, Makhmudov B. Saydinjon, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar**
USE OF TENSION-FREE HERNIOPLASTY IN SURGICAL TREATMENT OF STARGED ANTERIOR HERNIA ABDOMINAL WALL (LITERATURE REVIEW).....113
16. **Avazov A. Abdurakhim., Shakirov M. Bobur., Hakimov A. Erkin**
TREATMENT OF ISOLATED BURNS OF THE HAND AND FOOT IN A HUMID ENVIRONMENT WITH SILVER-CONTAINING PREPARATIONS.....120

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

17. **Fozilov A. Uktam**
DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF THE DIAGNOSIS OF DENTAL ANOMALIES AND DEFORMATIONS USING A COMPUTER PROGRAM.....126
18. **Nurova N. Shoxsanam**
THE INCIDENCE OF CHRONIC DISSEMINATED PERIODONTITIS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF OSTEOPOROSIS IN WOMEN OF FERTILE AGE WITH BREAST CANCER.....136
19. **Ibragimova Kh. Malika, Ruzikulova Sh. Munira**
PERIODONTAL STATUS ACCORDING TO THE CPITN INDEX IN PATIENTS WITH FATTY HEPATOSIS.....141
20. **Kamalova R. Feruza, Rakhimov Kh. Jahongir.**
INFLUENCE OF MAGNETOTHERAPY ON VARIOUS SYSTEMS OF THE BODY AND ON THE PROCESS OF WOUND HEALING IN CHILDREN WITH CLEFT LIP.....149
21. **Gaffarov A. Sunnatullo, Astanov M. Otabek**
DENTAL CONDITION OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES IN PATIENTS WITH PSYCHIATRIC PATHOLOGIES.....154
22. **Kamalova R. Feruza, Mamedova Sh. Nigina**
EVALUATION OF COMPLEX TREATMENT OF ODONTOGENIC PURULENT INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE JAWS.....161
23. **Agababyan R. Irina, Ismoilov M. Rajabboy**
SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATION IN ATHEROSCLEROSIS ON THE BACKGROUND OF CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS.....166
24. **Boymuradov A. Shukhrat, Ruzibayev R. Dilshod**
RESULTS OF ELIMINATING OF PERFORATION OF THE MAXILLARY SINUS BOTTOM USING PRF.....173
25. **Abasniya R. Surayyo**
LABORATORY INDICATORS OF IMPROVING METHODS OF TREATING PERIODONTITIS AMONG THE POPULATION OF KHOREZM REGION.....182
26. **Eronov Q. Yoqub**
THE INFLUENCE OF PATHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE MICROBIOCENOSIS OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES ON ORAL HYGIENE IN CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES.....187

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

27. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Nabiye R. Ozod, Raupova M. Kamola, Boltayev I. Anvar**
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ACOUSTIC REFLEX OF THE INTRA-EAR MUSCLES IN OCCUPATIONAL HEARING DISORDERS.....193

28. **Xatamov A. Jakhongir, Amonov E. Ergashevich**
MODERN APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF COMPLICATED FORMS OF
CHRONIC INFLAMMATION OF THE MIDDLE EAR.....200
29. **Lutfullayev U. Gairat, Ne`matov S. O`ktam, Khamraev Kh. Farid**
LOBULAR CAPILLARY HAEMANGIOMA OF THE NASAL CAVITY DURING
PREGNANCY: A CLINICAL CASE.....209
30. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Xayitov A. Alisher, Nabiyev R. Ozod, Dustboboyev S. Dilshod**
IMPROVEMENT OF THE SURGICAL APPROACH FOR CYSTIC LESIONS OF THE
MAXILLARY SINUS.....214

PEDIATRICS

31. **Rakhmatullaev A. Akmal, Terebaev A. Bilim, Mazhidov Kh. Temur**
MODERN VIEWS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT PAYRE'S SYNDROME IN
CHILDREN.....221
32. **Garifulina M. Lilya M., Goyibova S. Nargiza**
MICROALBUMINURIA AS AN INDICATOR OF METABOLIC DISORDERS IN
OBESITY CHILDREN.....227
33. **Yusupova U. Umida**
PECULIARITIES OF CYTOKINE STATUS IN EARLY CHILDREN WITH NON-SOCIAL
PNEUMONIA LIVING IN ECOLOGICAL REGIONS.....233
34. **Kuryazova M. Sharofat, Khudaynazarova R. Salomat**
FREQUENCY AND STRUCTURE OF BRONCHOPULMONARY PATHOLOGY IN
CHILDREN OF DIFFERENT AGE GROUPS.....241

CHILDREN SURGERY

35. **Yuldashev A. Botir, Murodova D. Malika**
ASSESSMENT OF CARDIORENAL SYNDROME IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE
NEPHRITIC SYNDROME.....247

PSYCHONEUROLOGY

36. **Rizaev A. Jasur, Khakimova Z. Sohuba**
BRAIN REGENERATION: STEM CELL THERAPY FOR NEURODEGENERATIVE
DISEASES.....255
37. **Kodirov A. Umid, Abdurakhimov Mukhiddin**
RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH
LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHY IN CHRONIC BRUCELLIOSIS.....262
38. **Kodirov A. Umid, Turdiev Dilmurod**
RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH
LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHY IN CASE OF HERPETIC INFECTION.....269
39. **Turaev M. Tolib, Kuchimova A. Charos**
CLINICAL SIGNIFICANS OF ANXIETY AND DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS IN PATIENTS
WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME.....275
40. **Muminov A. Bekzod, Matmurodov J. Rustambek, Khalimova M. Khanifa, Nazarova F. Madinabonu, Umirova M. Surayyo.**
CHANGED LEVELS OF INTERLEUKIN-6 IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE PATIENTS
WITH COVID-19.....281
41. **Mirjuraev M. Elbek, Samiev S. Asliddin, Urakov U. Shokir**
ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH
COGNITIVE CHANGES IN CHRONIC CEREBRAL CIRCULATION DISEASES.....289

ONCOLOGY AND GEMATOLOGY

42. **Ismailova A. Jadida, Yusupbekov A. Abrorjon, Tuychiyev D. Otabek**
STUDY OF HISTOPATHOLOGICAL STAGES OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE IN THE
EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF GASTRIC CANCER.....296
43. **Abdiyev Kattabek Makhmatovich**
COMPLICATIONS OF PRIMARY MYELOFIBROSIS AND TACTICS OF THEIR
TREATMENT.....303
44. **Azimova A. Makhbuba, Nasirova K. Khurshedakhon**
THYROID DYSFUNCTION IN BREAST CANCER.....316

REHABILITATION AND SPORTS MEDICINE

45. **Kamalova A. Yokutkhon, Sulaimonov Sh. Vakil**
FEATURES OF THE APPLICATION OF THERAPEUTIC PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN
PATIENTS WITH CERVICAL OSTEOCHONDROSIS.....325

MORPHOLOGY

46. **Kuryazov K. Akbar, Olimov Sh. Siddik**
AGE-RELATED CHANGES IN ORTHOPEDIC STATUS IN WOMEN OF FERTILE
AGE.....331
47. **Khoshimov L. Bobur, Akhmedova M. Sayyora**
REACTIVE CHANGES IN THE AORTA IN EXPERIMENTAL METABOLIC
SYNDROME.....339
48. **Muzaffarova Sh. Nargiza, Sheryigitova I. Nigina, Azizov M. Mardon**
A NEW PERSPECTIVE ON THE ROLE OF VITAMIN D IN THE HUMAN BODY.....346
49. **Abdusattarov A. Adahamjon Alisherovich, Juraeva A. Mohigul, Ashuralieva A. Mavlyuda.**
THE CONCEPT OF FUNCTIONAL DYSPEPSIA.....353
50. **Oripov S. Firdavs Suratovich, Eshkabilova T. Surayo**
IMPACT OF ENERGY DRINKS COMPONENTS ON THE HUMAN BODY AND ITS
COMPLICATIONS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....361
51. **RADJABOV B. Akhtam**
MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL
DEVELOPMENT OF MALES IN POSTNATAL ONTOGENESIS AND IN CHRONIC
ALCOHOLISM.....368
52. **TILYABOV Ikram, USMANOV Ravshan**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE KIDNEYS OF RATS IN DIABETES INDUCED
BY STREPTOZOTOCIN.....373

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

53. **Tilyakov B. Aziz, Tilyakov A. Xasan, Ayozboev A. Zuhridin, Nabiyev A. Muhammadi**
CRITERIA FOR THE CHOICE OF TREATMENT AND DIAGNOSIS OF COMBINED
CHEST INJURIES IN PEDIATRIC PRACTICE.....383
54. **Tilyakov A. Xasan, Tilyakov B. Aziz, Temurov A. Alisher, Nomozov N. Fazliddin**
OPTIMAL METHODS OF CARE FOR VICTIMS WITH COMBINED BONE AND
VASCULAR INJURIES OF THE LOWER EXTREMITIES.....390
55. **Eranov N. Sherzod, Tilyakov A. Khasan**
ASSESSMENT OF X-RAY INDICATORS OF INSTABILITY OF THE DISTAL
RADIOULNARY JOINT IN CHILDREN.....401

56. **Fattakhov A. Ravshan, Nuritdinov A. Ulugbek**
DISC DISLOCATIONS OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINTS (SCIENTIFIC REVIEW).....408

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

57. **Iskandarov I. Alisher, Kaidarov A. Makhammadali**
EXPERT ASSESSMENT OF THE INFORMATION CONTENT OF CLINICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS DURING THERMAL EXPOSURE ETHYLENE GLYCOL.....414
58. **Turonov Bobur Sobir ugli, Iskandarov Alisher Iskandarovitch**
VISCERO-IRIDAL REFLEX CONNECTIONS IN THE MECHANISM OF IRIDOLOGY.....420
59. **Davranova E. Aziza, Toshmamatov Sh. Alimardon, Tashev Sh. Ulmas, Ganiev N. Sobirzhon, Kushbakov M. Akbar**
FORENSIC CHEMICAL INVESTIGATIONS AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS.....425

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

60. **Yarmuxamedova A. Nargiza, Yakubova S. Nigina, Mirzaeva U. Adolat**
CLINICAL AND LABORATORY CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH TICK-BORNE RICKETSIOSIS IN THE SAMARKAND REGION.....434
61. **Achilova M. Matlyuba, Shodiyeva A. Dilafruz**
ASSESSMENT OF THE SAFETY OF HIGHLY ACTIVE ANTIRETROVIRAL THERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH HIV INFECTION.....448
62. **Imamova A. Ilmira**
RELEVANCE OF COVID-19 IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC VIRAL HEPATITIS.....453
63. **Allaberganova S. Zumrad, Karimova A. Maqsuda, Rajapov Y. Shahzod, Kurbanbaeva K. Dilnoza**
STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND PROTEOLYTIC PROPERTIES OF YEAST-LIKE FUNGI OF THE GENUS CANDIDA.....461
64. **Oslanov A. Absamat, Kodirov F. Jonibek, Samibaeva Kh. Umida, Suyarov A. Ulugbek, Qozieva L. Dilobar, Djumanazarov N. Sardorbek, Boysunov Ch. Shokhzod**
SOME ASPECTS OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF MEASLES IN CHILDREN UNDER ONE YEAR OF ONE YEAR.....467

OPHTHALMOLOGY

65. **Yusupov F. Azamat, Khusanbaev Sh. Khasanjon, Abdullaeva I. Saida.**
COMPLICATIONS OF DIABETIC RETINOPATHY AND THEIR SOLUTION.....475
66. **Xamidullayev F. Firdavs. Normatova M. Nargiza Nematulloev K. Tukhtasin**
EFFECTIVENESS AND SAFETY OF BROLUCIZUMAB IN TREATING DIABETIC MACULAR EDEMA.....482
67. **Karimova Kh. Muyassar, Ubaydullaev O. Sardor**
CLINICAL CASE OF IOL IMPLANTATION IN POSTVITRECTOMY EYE WITH APHAKIA.....491

UDK 614.2:616.31-

TILYAKOV Aziz Burievich

Candidate of Sciences, docent

TILYAKOV Xasan Azizovich

PhD

AYOZBOEV Zuhridin Alimqul o'g'li

resident of the department

NABIYEV Muhammadi Abdunaim o'g'li

resident of the department

Tashkent Pediatrics Institute of Medicine

CRITERIA FOR THE CHOICE OF TREATMENT AND DIAGNOSIS OF COMBINED CHEST INJURIES IN PEDIATRIC PRACTICE

For citation: Tilyakov B. Aziz, Tilyakov A. Xasan, Ayozbekov A. Zuhridin, Nabiyeu A. Muhammadi. Criteria for the choice of treatment and diagnosis of combined chest injuries in pediatric practice. // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 2, pp. 383-389

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.11301237>

ABSTRACT

63 children with chest injuries of varying severity and localization were admitted to the Center for Pediatric Surgery of SamMU for the period 1996-2022. There were 39 children with combined chest injury. Thoracotomy was performed on 8 children, 22 underwent video thoracoscopic surgical interventions. The age ranged from 3 to 15 years. A retrospective analysis of the treatment of 39 children with combined injuries was carried out. The patients were divided into 4 groups according to the severity of shock according to the Algover classification. As a result of a retrospective analysis of the use of various surgical approaches, the severity of the existing injuries and the possibility of their elimination, it was shown that the Algover shock index allows fairly objectively predicting the possibility of performing therapeutic VTS in children with combined chest injury and is directly correlated with the probability of BBTRISS survival, which correlate with the degree of shock and existing injuries in the patient.

Keywords: videothoracoscopy, combined chest injury, shock index, pediatric surgery, children.

ТИЛЯКОВ Азиз Буриевич

К.м.н. доцент

ТИЛЯКОВ Хасан Азизович

PhD

Аязбаев Зухриддин Аликул ўгли

Резинт ординатуры

Набиев Мухаммади Абдунаим ўгли

Резинт ординатуры

КРИТЕРИИ ВЫБОРА ЛЕЧЕНИЯ И ДИАГНОСТИКИ СОЧЕТАННЫХ ТРАВМ ГРУДНОЙ КЛЕТКИ В ПЕДИАТРИЧЕСКОЙ ПРАКТИКЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В центр детской хирургии СамМУ за период 1996-2022 гг. с травмами грудной клетки различной тяжести и локализации поступило 63 ребенка. С сочетанной травмой грудной клетки были 39 детей. Торакотомия выполнена 8 детям, 22 выполнены видеоторакоскопические оперативные вмешательства. Возраст составил от 3 до 15 лет. Проведен ретроспективный анализ лечения 39 детей с сочетанными травмами. Пациенты были разделены на 4 группы соответственно тяжести шока по классификации Альговера. В результате ретроспективного анализа применения различных хирургических доступов, тяжести имеющихся повреждений и возможности их устранения показано, что шоковый индекса Альговера позволяет достаточно объективно прогнозировать возможность выполнения лечебной ВТС у детей с сочетанной травмой грудной клетки и напрямую взаимосвязан с вероятностью выживаемости BBTRISS, которые коррелируют со степенью шока и имеющимися травмами у пациента.

Ключевые слова: видеоторакоскопия, сочетанная травма грудной клетки, шоковый индекс, детская хирургия, дети.

TILYAKOV Aziz Burievich

t.f.n. dotsent

TILYAKOV Xasan Azizovich

PhD

AYOZBOEV Zuhridin Alimqul o'g'li

Klinik ordinator

NABIYEV Muhammadi Abdunaim o'g'li

Klinik ordinator

Toshkent pediatriya tibbiyot instituti

ПЕДИАТРИК АМАЛИЙОТДА КО'КРАК QAFASI QO'SHMA JAROHLARINI DAVOLASH VA TASHXISLASHNI TANLASH MEZONLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Samarqand Davlat tibbiyot universiteti qoshidagi bolalar xirurgiya markazini 1996-2022 yillarda 63 ta bolalarda ko'krak qafasini xar xil og'irlikdagi jarohatlari va lokalizatsiyasi taxlili o'tqazildi. Ko'krak qafasining aralash jarohatlari bilan 39 ta bemor. 8 ta bemorga torakotomiya, 22 ta bemorga videotorokoskopik operativ aralashur o'tqazilgan. Bemorlarning yoshi 3 – 15 ni tashkil qildi. 39 ta ko'krak qafasini aralash jarohatlari bilan davolangan bemorlarini retrospektiv taxlili o'tqazildi. Bemorlar shok xolatining Algovver klassifikatsiyasi bo'yicha 4 ta guruxga bo'lindi. Xirurgik kirish bemorning og'irlik darajasi va Algovver shok indeksi taxlili asosida amalga oshirildi, va uni VTS yo'li bilan davolash ob'ektiv bashoratlandi. Bollarda ko'krak qafasi jarohatlaridan keyingi yashab ketishi Vvtriss shkalasi shok darajasini va bemordagi jarohatlarni korrelyatsiyasi bilan amalga oshirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ko'krak qafasi aralash japroxlari, torakotomiya, shok indeksi, bolar xirurgiyasi.

Kirish.

Bugungi kunda bolalarda ko'krak qafasining aralash jarohatlarini davolash va tashxislash shoshilinch pediatriya xirurgiyasida dolzarb muamolardan bo'lib kelmoqda (Davlyatov S.B. va hammualliflar 2008,). Shunda ko'pkina xollarda ko'krak qafasi organlarini og'irlik darajasini adekvat baxolash murakkabdir. Qon yo'qotganlik xajmi, jarohat lokalizatsiyasi bevosida davolash taktikasi va tibbiy yordam ko'rsatish ketma-ketligini tanlashda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelinadi.

Vidieotorokoskopiyaning to'plangan tajribalariga qaramasdan, ko'krak qafasining jarohatlarida, jarroh oldida bemorning holati VTS amaliyotini o'tkazishga imkon beradimi yoki yo'qmi, asosiy VTS amalga oshirishda asosiy sharoit bu bemorning gemodinamik xolatidir (Isakov Yu. F., Beyker S. P., Boyd C. R.).

Tekshirishlar maqsadi. Ko'krak qafasi jarohatida Allover shok indeksini qo'llagan xolda VTS qo'llash imkoniyatini bashoratlash.

Tadqiqot maqsadi. Gemodinamik ko'rsatgichlarni retrospektiv va SIA indeksini baholagan holda ko'krak qafasi jarohati og'ir darajali shok holatlarida VTS ni qo'llash.

Material va usullar: Samarqand bolalar xirurgiya ilmiy markazida 63 ta bemor bolalar 1996-2022 yillarda yakkalangan va qo'shma ko'krak qafasi jarohati bilan taxlil qilingan. Plevra bo'shlig'i diagnostik punktsiyasi, VTS, torokokomiya 16 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolarda amalga oshirilgan.

Jarohat turlari bo'yicha; 29 bemor (46%) yo'l-transport travmasi bilan, 21 bemor (33,3%) balandlikdan yiqilish, ko'krak qafasini chanchilgan - kesilgan jarohati bilan -13 (20,7%) va 39 (61,9) ta bemor aralash jarohatlar bilan xarakterlanadi. (1-jadval).

Bemorlarni aralash jarohat turi orqali bo'linishi

Aralash jarohat turi	Soni
Ko'krak qafasi+ BMJ	12(30,8%)
Ko'krak qafasi+qo'l, oyoq jarohatlari	14(35,9%)
Ko'krak qafasi+BMJ+ qul-oyoq jarohati+umurtqa pog'onasi jarohati	6(15,4%)
Ko'krak qafasi+BMJ+ qul-oyoq jarohati+umurtqa pog'onasi jarohati+qorin bo'shlig'i jarohati	3(7,7%)
Ko'krak qafasi+oyok-qo'l jarohati+umurtqa pog'onasi jarohati	1 (2,5%)
Ko'krak qafasi+ qorin bo'shlig'i jarohati+ oyoq -qo'l jarohati	3 (7,7%)
Jami	39 (100%)

Aralash jarohatlar bilan 39 ta bemordan bosh miya jarohati 21 (43%) bemorda kuzatilgan. 24 ta bemorda esa qo'shma jarohatlar oyoq -qo'l jarohatlari qorin bo'shlig'i jarohatlari bilan kuzatilgan. 33 (952,4%) bemorda davolash - diagnostik muolaja punktsiya plevra bo'shlig'ini punktsiyasi bilan chegaralangan, qolgan 47,6% bemorlarda interplevral davomiy qon ketish kuzatilgan va 8 ta bemorga torakotomiya, 22 ta bemorga esa VTS amaliyoti o'tqazilgan (2-jadval).

Torakotomiya da aniqlangan ko'krak ichi jarohatlari

Ko'krak ichi jarohatlari	N=8
O'pka jarohati (sanchilgan -kesilgan jarohat)	2
Qovurg'alar aro arteriya jarohati	2
Suyak bo'laklari bilan o'pkani jarohati	1
O'pka paski qismini jarohati	1
O'pka parinxemasini yiritilishi	2

Jadval 3

Diagnostik vidieotorokoskopiya da aniqlangan ko'krak ichi jarohatlari

Ko'krak ichi jarohatlari	N=22
O'pka jarohati (sanchilgan -kesilgan jarohat)	4
Pnevmtoroks (visseral plevrani yirtilishi o'pka parinxema butinligi saqlangan)	6
Plevra bo'shlig'ida va o'pka parinxemasida yot jism	1

Qovurg'alar aro arteriya jarohati	2
O'pka venasini jarohati	1
O'pka tubini yorilishi	1
O'pkaning lat eyishi intraparenximatoz qon quyilish	2
O'pka parinxemasining yirtilishi	3

Ko'krak qafasini qo'shma jarohatlarida VTS amaliyotini bajarish ko'krak qafasi bilan jarohatlangan bemorlarni gemodinamik ko'rsatgichlarini retrospektiv taxlili asosida 39 (61%) bemorda amalga oshirildi.

Bemorlarning ahvolini baxolashda bizlar ISS anatomik kriteriyasidan, RTS fiziologik kriteriyasidan [8], TRISS fiziologik ko'rsatkichidan [9], BBTRISS yashab qolish imkoniyatini bashoratlash koefitsentidan foydalangan holda VTS ga potentsial moyillik borligi aniqlandi. SIA – Allovera shok indeksi - koefitsienti, yurak qisqarish chastotasini sistolik bosimga bo'lish orqali aniqlandi.

Natijalar taxlili. SIA indeksini inobatga olgan holda araplash jarohat olgan bemorlar shokning og'irligi bo'yicha bo'lindi (4-jadval).

O'rta kursatgich sia bemorlar soni ABS.,(%)

ISS

RTS V ko'krak bo'shlig'ida qon maqjudligi, ml t jarohat olishgacha bo'lgan mutdat,s.

Jadval 4

SIA indeksi bo'yicha ko'krak qafasini aralash jarohatining bo'linishi

SIA	O'rta ko'rsatgich sia	Bemorlar soni ABS.,(%)	ISS	RTS	V ko'krak bo'shlig'ida qon maqjudligi / ml	t jarohat olishgacha bo'lgan mutdat,s.	BBTRISS
< 1,0	0,74±0,06	22 (73,5)	8,77±1,85	7,834±0,02	255±185	2,35±1,35	0,961±0,018
1,0-1,5	1,08±0,06	4 (13,3)	11,71±2,23	7,787±0,14	387±186	1,45±1,25	0,921±0,019
1,5-2,0	1,67±0,06	2 (6,6)	14,81±3,05	6,757±0,42	586±258	1,35±0,45	0,746±0,013
>2,0	3,12±11,2	2 (6,6)	25,9±5,11	5,975±0,48	1078±325	1,38±0,55	0,452±0,012

Jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki 4 indens SIA< 1,0 (shokning engil darajasi) aralash jarohatlar bilan 22 bemorda (73,5%) kuzatilgan. SIA ko'rsatgichlarining keyinchalik o'sib borishi ISS indeksini o'sib borishi va RTS indeksini kamayib borishi bilan bog'liqligi, bemorlarning anatomik jarohatlarini og'irligi fiziologik buzilishlar bilan kuchaya boradi.

Plevral bo'shliqdagi qonning o'rta xajmdan proporsional ravishda o'sib borishi jarohatning og'irlanishini ko'rsatadi. Aralash jarohatlarda og'irlik daraja va jarohatlar soni (ISS, RTS) SIA indeksi va BBTRISS tirik qolish imkoniyati Informatik ko'inishga egadir. Agarda shok indeksi SIA< 1,0 BBTRISS= 0,961±0,018, unda tirik qoldish imkoniyati 96,1±1,8% ga teng bo'ladi, SIA>2,0 BBTRISS= 0,452±0,012 esa tirik qolish imkoniyati keskin kamayadi va 45,2±1,2% teng bo'lib qoladi. Bu ushbu toifadagi bemorlarda letal xolat yuqori darajada ekanligidan dalolat beradiki.

SIA ko'rsatgichini solishtirish maqsadida jarohatni og'irligi, organ va lokalizasiyaga bog'liqligi quyidagi jadvalda berilgan (5-jadval).

Jadval 5

Ko'krak qafasi aralash jarohati strukturasi SIA indeksi ko'rsatgichinig o'zgarishi

SIA	Bemorlar soni ABS., (%)	Jaroxalangan organ va soxa						
		O'pka parinxemasi	Magistral qon tomirlar	Qovurg'alararo qon tomirlar	Tayanch harakat tizimi	Qorin bo'shlig'i	Bosh miya	Va boshqa jarohatlar

< 1,0	22 (73,5)	11	-	2	9	1	8	4
1,0-1,5	4 (13,3)	9	-	3	10	3	9	3
1,5-2.0	2 (6,6)	-	2	-	1	1	1	-
>2.0	2 (6,6)	-	1	-	1	1	1	-

Jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki SIA < 1,0 ko'pincha o'pka parenxima jarohatida -11 ta xolat, 2 qovurg'alar aro tomirlar jarohati kuzatilgan, 9-ta xolatda esa tayanch –xarakat tizimi jarohatlari va 8-ta xolat bom miya jarohati bilan. Ya'ni keskin intensiv qon ketish xaraktenga ega bo'lgan jarohat yo'q. Intensiv qon yo'qotiyatgan bemorlar shoshilinch ravishda davolash muassasalariga zudlig bilan etqazilib va ularda og'ir gemmoragik shok xolatlari kuzatilmagan.

SIA = 1,0-1,5 jarohat xarakteri quyidagi klinik ko'rinishga ega. 9 – ta bemorda o'rta darajadagi shok xolati qovurg'alararo arteriya jarohatida kuzatilgan. sootvetstvenno. Bunday kategoriyadagi bemorlarda uch marotiba ko'proq qorin bo'shlig'i, bish miya, Tayans-xarakat tizimi jarohatlarilda 9-10 ta xolat kuzatildi.

SIA = 1,5-2,0 bemorlarda og'ir shok xolati katta qon tomirlarni jarohati, massiv qon yo'qotish og'ir bosh miya jarohatida kuzatildi.

SIA > 2.0 (o'ta og'ir shok xolati) og'ir bosh miya jarohati, o'pka tubidagi magistral tomirlar jarohati, qorin bo'shliq organlarinig jarohati, bunday aralash jarohatlar bilan bemorlar to'liq letal xolat bilan kechadi. Davolash maqsadida VTS ni qo'llash mumkinligini bashoratlash uchun retrospektiv xirurgik kirishni ko'krak qafasini aralash jarohatlari bilan bolarda SIA indeksiga bog'liqligini ko'rib chiqdik (6-jadval).

Жадвал 5

SIA indeksiga tayangan xolda jarroxlik yondashuvini retrospektiv baxolash.

SIA indeksi	Bemorlar soni ABS.,(%)	Operativ usullar			
		Davolash BTC		Torakotomiya	
		a	б	a	б
< 1,0	22 (73,5)	16	1	3	2
1,0-1,5	4 (13,3)	2	1	1	-
1,5-2.0	2 (6,6)	-	1*	1	-
>2.0	2 (6,6)	-	1*	1	-

a-oqlangan, б-oqlanmagan, *- (konversiya)

Jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki SIA indeksiga tayangan xolda xirurgik yondashuvlar quyidagicha.

SIA < 1,0 bemorlarda retrospektiv taxlil 16 - ta xolatda VTS ko'rsatma bo'lib operatsiya endoxirurgik yo'l bilan yakunlandi. Bita xolatda VTS sanasion xarakterga ega bo'lib boshqa muoloja bajarilmadi, bu xolatga ko'rsatma bo'lib pleva bo'shliqdagi qon drenaj trubka orqali chiqdi, yangi qon ketish manbai kuzatilmadi, bundan tashqari plevral yiringli infeksiya xolati kuzatilmadi.

5 bemordan 2 ta xolatda giperdiagnostika ustunlik qilib torakotomiya qilingan, vaxolanki ularga endoxirurgik davolash usulini o'tqazish mumkin bo'lgan. Jarohat og'ir xarakterga ega bo'lmagan.

Bemorlar uchun SIA= 1.0-1.5 bilan indeksi tekshiruv davomida VTS o'g'irlanishining 2-holatini retrospektiv tahlil qilish. 1-gemorroyni olib tashlash operatsiyasi, gemorroyni olib tashlash operatsiyasi, gemorroyni olib tashlash operatsiyasi, bundai gemorroyni olib tashlash operatsiyasi, belgilangan torakotomiya.

SIA=1,5-2,0 bitt kasallanish indeksi diagnostik HTS quyoshi bilan plevra bo'shlig'i kengayadi va natijada arteriyalar har kvadrat dyuym uchun qiziydi. Gemorroiy, gematomalar va arteriyalarning osteoxondrozini olib tashlash bo'yicha operatsiya natijasida asoratlar aniqlangan bo'lishi mumkin.

SIA > 2.0 bu shuni anglatadiki, zarba paytida bemorga VTS tashxisi qo'yiladi va Konventsiya yordamida ingl. Bunday VTS bosimi ostida savodsiz va torakotomiya vaqti cheklangan.

Xulosa.

Bolalarda ko'krak qafasini aralash jarohatlarida SIA shok indeksini qo'llash VTS amaliyotini o'tqazishda uni aniq bashoratlaydi va BB_{TRISS} tirik qolish imkoniyatini shok darajalari bemordagi jarohatlarni korrelyasiyalaydi.

Davolash VTS amaliyotini SIA<1,0 bilan bemorlarga o'tqazish maqsadga muvofiq. Retrospektiv taxlilda bu guruhda konversii bo'lmadi.

SIA=1,0-1,5 25% xolatda davolash VTS asosiz va katta xavf endoxirurgik amaliyot natijasiz yoki bemor xayotiga zarar etqazadi Shuning uchun bunday bemorlarda VTS ga qiyinchilik bo'lsa konversiya o'tqazish zarur.

VTS ga SIA>1,5 qarshi ko'rsatma bo'ladi ko'krak qafasini keng va og'ir jarohatlari endoxirurgik operatsiyalar natija bermaydi va bunday bemorlarga aktiv xirurgik yo'l bilan yondashish kerak.

REFERENCES | ЧОККИ | ИҚТИБОСЛАР:

1. Arkhipov D.M. Videothoracoscopy in the diagnosis and treatment of chest wounds: diss.candidate of Medical Sciences. Moscow, 1999;3(2),55-57.(in Russ).
2. Davlyatov S.B. Therapeutic tactics for open and closed injuries of the organs of the thoracic cavity in children./ Ibodullosov H.U.// In the collection of Materials of the Russian Symposium of Pediatric surgeons "Traumatic intracavitary bleeding in children. Resuscitation and surgical aspects". Yekaterinburg.-2008;2(1),88-89. (in Russ).
3. Zhestkov K.G. Minimally invasive surgery for complicated closed chest injury. /Barsky B.V.// Materials of the international conference "New technologies in military field surgery and surgery of peacetime injuries". - St. Petersburg.- 2006;4(2), 75-76. (in Russ).
4. Isakov Yu.F. Thoracoscopic and video-assisted operations on chest organs in children./ Stepanov E.A., Razumovsky A.Yu.// Surgery. – 2003;.3(1), 22-25. (in Russ).
5. Safarov Zafar Fayzullayevich, Khakimov Jasur Pulatovich, Akhmatalieva Mayram Akhmatalievna, Alimov Akhror Abdurasulovich Diagnostic significance of the Algovner index for early recognition of shock in children // Problems of Science. 2019;1(1),138. (in Russ).
6. Tilyakov A.B., Tilyakov H.A. Nazarov S.P. The use of minimally invasive technologies in the treatment of the musculoskeletal system in patients with polythoma // Journal of Biomedicine and practice 2023; 4(3), 335-345. (in Russ).
7. Allgower M. Dtsch Med Wschr. / C. Burri, A. Schock index// 1997;1(4), 1947-1950.
8. Baker S.P. The Injury Severity Score: a method for describing patients with multiple injuries and evaluating emergency care./ B. O'Neil, W. Haddon, W.B. Long // J Trauma.- 1974;5(1),187—196.
9. Boyd C.R. Evaluating Trauma Care: The TRISS Method Trauma Score and the Severity Score./ M.A. Tolson, W.S. Copes.// J Trauma.-1987;5(2), 370—378.
10. Champion H.R. A Revision of the Trauma Score./ W.J. Sacco, W.S. Copes// J Trauma.- 1989;2(1), 623—629.

Статья поступила в редакцию 03.03.2024; одобрена после рецензирования 21.04.2024; принята к публикации 26.04.2024.

The article was submitted 03.03.2024; approved after reviewing 21.04.2024; accepted for publication 26.04.2024.

Информация об авторах:

Тияков Азиз Буриевич - к.м.н., профессор, ректор. Ташкентский педиатрический медицинский институт, Ташкент, Узбекистан. E-mail: tiliakov@bk.ru, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9743-0482>

Тияков Хасан Азизович- PhD, заведующий кафедры ФПДО травматологии-ортопедии, нефрохирургии и офтальмологии. Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет,

Самарканд, Узбекистан. E-mail: shaxxas.tilyakov@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-557-7302>

Аёзбоев Зухриддин - резидент ординатуры кафедры ФПДО травматологии-ортопедии, нефрохирургии и офтальмологии. Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, Самарканд, Узбекистан. E-mail: zuhriddin09a@gmail.com

Набиев Мухаммади - резидент ординатуры кафедры ФПДО травматологии-ортопедии, нефрохирургии и офтальмологии. Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, Самарканд, Узбекистан. E-mail: nabiyevmuhammadi41@gmail.com

Источники финансирования: Работа не имела специального финансирования.

Конфликт интересов: Авторы декларируют отсутствие явных и потенциальных конфликтов интересов, связанных с публикацией настоящей статьи.

Вклад авторов:

Тияков А.Б. — идеологическая концепция работы, написание текста; редактирование статьи; Тияков Х.А. — сбор и анализ источников литературы, написание текста.

Аёзбоев З- написание статьи, внесение изменений в текст, обработка материалов.

Набиев М - написание статьи, внесение изменений в текст, обработка материалов.

Information about the authors:

Aziz B. Tilyakov - PhD, Professor, Rector. Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan. E-mail: tiliakov@bk.ru, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9743-0482>

Xasan A. Tilyakov - PhD, Head of the Department of Traumatology-Orthopedics, Nephrosurgery and Ophthalmology. Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. E-mail: shaxxas.tilyakov@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-557-7302>

Zukhriddin Ayozeboev- is a resident of the Department of Traumatology-Orthopedics, Nephrosurgery and Ophthalmology. Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. E-mail: zuhriddin09a@gmail.com

Mukhammadi Nabiyev - is a resident of the Department of Traumatology-Orthopedics, Nephrosurgery and Ophthalmology. Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. E-mail: nabiyevmuhammadi41@gmail.com

Sources of funding: The work did not receive any specific funding.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no explicit or potential conflicts of interest associated with the publication of this article.

Contribution of the authors:

Tilyakov A.B. — the ideological concept of the work, writing the text; editing the article;

Tilyakov H.A. — collection and analysis of literature sources, writing a text.

Aezboev Z- writing an article, making changes to the text, processing materials.

Nabiev M - writing an article, making changes to the text, processing materials.

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 2

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000